

INTEGRATED LEARNING AS THE MAIN CONDITION FOR SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER

¹Boranbaeva A.S., ²Rezhep A.S.

¹National State University named after Jusup Balasagyn, Bishkek, Kyrgyz Republic

²M. Auezov South Kazakhstan University, Shymkent, Kazakhstan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11000649>

Abstract. *The purpose of the article is to consider one of the urgent problems of modern education - the problem of integrated education for children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD).*

The article presents the reasons due to which children with ASD do not receive or receive less opportunity to integrate into ordinary society and receive a standard education, as well as techniques and methods that allow such children to adapt to the conditions of ordinary life and education.

The article describes in detail the program for the adaptation of children with autism, taking into account both the severity of the course of autism, the psychological characteristics of the child, and the characteristics of the presentation of educational material.

The article points out that an important factor in successful integrated learning is the creation of an adequate educational environment, especially the organization and self-organization of the child. The article presents the developed state programs that help solve these problems, but need some adjustment.

Keywords: *children with disabilities, inclusive education, program, autism, adaptation.*

The education of children with disabilities and, in particular, children with autism spectrum disorder, is not only a socio-pedagogical task, but also one of the main and integral conditions for successful socialization, ensuring their full formation as a member of society.

Regardless of the level of readiness of the school to accept children with disabilities, a child with autism faces many problems, the degree of complexity of which is determined not only by the severity of autistic disorders, but also by the quality of previous correctional work, as well as the availability of appropriate conditions for receiving education.

M.M. Semago argues that support for children with disabilities should be closely combined with both health protection and a dynamic assessment of the child's adaptability in the educational environment. A strict, individually determined dosage of educational loads on a child with disabilities is necessary. On the one hand, they must be optimal and sufficient for the full development of the child, on the other hand, they must not go beyond the limits of individually acceptable loads for a given child in order not to provoke a breakdown in adaptation [1, p. 74].

Often, when studying in general education schools, children with ASD are isolated from the society of normally developing peers and have limited contacts, which leads to disruption of social adaptation and socialization. Therefore, it is so important to provide children of this category with social and pedagogical support and the creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions for the integration of children with autism spectrum disorder into the general education

environment, aimed at overcoming the difficulties of socialization in a general education institution.

Integrated learning means that students with different levels of mental and physical development study in the same class. They enjoy going to extracurricular activities, participating in student government together, going to sports meetings, and playing with other children.

Integrated learning is a process that appreciates the diversity and unique contributions of each student to learning. Indeed, in an inclusive environment, every child feels safe and part of the group [2, p. 88].

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the problem of inclusive education was raised in the 90s, mainly by professors and candidates of technical sciences. Kazakh scientist, Ph.D. Suleymenova R.A., with the support of various international organizations, organized research activities to create a state system for the inclusion of children with disabilities in the general educational process; under her leadership, the form of methodological, legal and information support for special education was determined. The result of this activity is the actualization of the problems of inclusive education and the inclusion of children with disabilities in the general educational environment [3]. Under the leadership of Suleymenova R.A. modeling of the system of early correctional and pedagogical assistance was carried out, models of new services were organized, developed and implemented, which later began to exist as independent types of new special education organizations: these are psychological, medical and pedagogical consultations (PMPC), rehabilitation centers (RC), offices psychological and pedagogical correction (PPC), lekoteka. All these new types of organizations were included in the Law "On social and medical-pedagogical correctional support for children with disabilities," developed on the initiative and under the leadership of R.A. Suleymenova. and adopted in 2002.

Since 2000, the Republic of Kazakhstan has been developing a new educational policy for children with disabilities, actively searching for optimal ways of socialization, upbringing, education, social support and adaptation of children. In the field of special education, innovative processes for integrating children into the educational environment of healthy peers have been widely introduced. During the same period, the study of innovative areas continues in order to create optimal conditions for social adaptation and integration of children with disabilities into society.

In the studies of scientists of the Kyrgyz Republic until the mid-90s, in particular, J.S. Barsanaeva (2019), G.T. Karabalayeva (2019), R.K. Nurmaganbetova and M.A. Tokbergenova (2019) and others note that regarding the education of children with disabilities, there was segregation - separating them in the learning process from healthy children. Children with special needs studied in special schools and boarding schools. Later, in the republic, along with the traditional system, they began to introduce inclusive education - teaching children with disabilities in regular preschool and school organizations together with their peers [3,4,5].

The Ministry of Education and Science of the Kyrgyz Republic, the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) are teaming up to implement inclusive education in Kyrgyzstan. The government has developed a Concept for the introduction of inclusive education in Kyrgyzstan to improve learning opportunities for children with disabilities. To implement it, a two-year project is being launched to support inclusive education and improve learning. The main idea contained in the Concept is that inclusive education is considered as a comprehensive process of ensuring equal access for all

children, including children with special educational needs, to quality education; ways are outlined for organizing the education of children with autism spectrum disorder in regular preschool and general education organizations, together with by their peers [6].

The main problems of a child with autism spectrum disorder are impaired communication with the world, limited mobility, poor communication with peers and adults, limited contact with nature, lack of access to a number of cultural values, and sometimes even to basic education. Solving the problem of educating children with disabilities is currently relevant due to the objective difficulties of providing social services and integrating the child into society. These difficulties can be biological, mental, social and complex, manifesting themselves to varying degrees.

According to Kazakh scientists A.K. Kaplieva and K.A. Dautova (2014), the main problem of socialization is the deviation from the individual development of disabled children. This manifests itself in the emotionally voluntary sphere, disruption of social interaction, self-doubt, decreased self-organization and determination, which leads to a weakening of “personal strength.” Socialization of children with disabilities is the integration of these children into society in order to acquire and assimilate certain values and generally accepted norms of behavior necessary for life in society. One of the conditions for the successful socialization of children with disabilities is their preparation for independent living, support and assistance in entering “adult life,” which requires, first of all, the creation of pedagogical conditions in the family and educational institutions for the social adaptation of children [7].

The problems of inclusive education of children with disabilities in the Republic of Kazakhstan are revealed in the works of Kh. S. Eralieva (2016), D.D. Eshpanova and A.K. Jalmukhamedova (2014), Z.A. Movkebaeva, I.A. Oralkanova, D.S. Jakupova (2014) and others. In their research, the authors reveal the features of the implementation of inclusive education and the prospects for its development in Kazakhstan. The inclusion of students with special educational needs in mainstream schools is one of the current and important issues facing the education community at the national and international levels [8,9,10].

In general, the relevance and growing interest in inclusive education in Kazakhstan is associated with an increase in the number of children with special educational needs and the need to improve the quality of life of people with disabilities through the humanization of education. At the same time, the development of interest and need for inclusive education is due to the growth of social interaction between people, the development of information and communication technologies, which make the best practices of developed countries accessible to a wide range of people, thereby increasing the need to prepare children with disabilities for life in the modern world, to ensure improvement their quality of life, participation in social networks, etc.

Based on this, researchers Zh.I. Sardarov and N.S. Zhumasheva (2017) give the following definition: Inclusive education is a policy and process that allows all children to participate in all programs. The difference in approaches lies in the recognition that “we are changing society not the other way around, but in a way that takes into account and adapts to the individual needs of people. The simple physical inclusion of children with ASD in the general education environment does not constitute inclusive education” [11].

According to Kazakh scientists (Kh.S. Eralieva, D.D. Eshpanova, Z.A. Movkebaeva et al. (2014)), if teachers cannot organize the educational process taking into account the individual needs of each child with ASD, then the chances for the full inclusion of these children in education

are significantly reduced. As a result, their motivation to study decreases, learning outcomes decrease and life prospects are limited [7,8,9].

A child with autism should have the opportunity to follow models of adequate social behavior of other children, which will contribute to his further social development.

In this regard, it should be noted that the State Educational Standard naturally raises the question of the factors and conditions necessary for the successful implementation of the task of creating a comfortable environment for the development of the child.

According to most global and international studies, the main problems of children with autism spectrum disorders that prevent them from learning in an inclusive classroom in a general education school are:

- difficulties in organizing one's own activities and behavior, in particular, productive educational activities;
- pronounced unevenness and specificity of development of mental functions;
- specificity and insufficient development of cognitive activity in general;
- difficulties in establishing productive interactions with other people;
- pronounced difficulties in social-emotional interaction;
- the need for a special organization of educational space;
- the need to use special techniques and methods when teaching them.

The main goal of an educational institution is to create organizational and pedagogical conditions for children with autism spectrum disorders, to create special educational programs for the development and social adaptation of such students. To do this, it is necessary to create optimal conditions for the development of positive opportunities for every child studying in an inclusive classroom. With inclusive education, obtaining quality knowledge is available to all students, regardless of individual capabilities.

In organizational and pedagogical terms, the educational space of a school should be a fairly flexible structure that allows the special educational needs of students, including those with autism spectrum disorders, to be taken into account in the most optimal way, to create special learning conditions and to provide the necessary psychological and pedagogical support for the educational process.

Due to the fact that in autism the mechanism for processing sensory information is qualitatively different, the use of special furniture, a gentle exercise regime and a "sensory diet" that prevents sensory overload are required. It is important to understand that vulnerability to information overload is one of the characteristics of children with autism.

The uneven development of the psyche inherent in autism, the presence of special, often overvalued interests, causes additional difficulties in mastering the material of the school curriculum in comparison with children with typical development, and, accordingly, requires adaptation of educational programs [12, p. 44].

For students with autism, adaptation of educational material should be carried out in the following areas:

- methodological adaptation (for example, the use of visual support or alternative communication);
- program adaptation (for example, different educational tasks for different children within one exercise, reducing the number or simplifying goals depending on the psychophysical characteristics of the child).

The development of an educational program for a student with autistic disorders should take into account not only his characteristics and capabilities, but also the level of his educational skills, independent work skills, and the uneven development of different aspects of mental development in general.

Considering the unpredictability of the dynamics of autism spectrum disorders, it is necessary to systematically monitor how well the chosen version of the adapted general education program corresponds to the student's capabilities, and what are the reasons for the difficulties that arise.

As foreign experience shows, in some cases, at the stage of a child's adaptation to learning conditions, the accompaniment of a tutor (assistant, teaching assistant) becomes a necessary condition.

It is known that an autistic child experiences significant difficulty in freely organizing himself in space and time, difficulties in interacting with children and adults, often manifested as an inability to navigate a specific communicative or educational situation. This requires special work to help manage an autistic child's life at school. Such work contributes to the creation of a certain, initially quite rigid stereotype of school life and personal behavior. Therefore, a separate task when organizing the educational activities of a child with autism is the creation of external

The most important external marker of changes in the sequence of actions and lessons is the schedule, which should be clear and visible to the child. It's good if there is a complete schedule of lessons and lessons for the current day on all days of the week on the wall next to the board. Such a hint makes the child's life more predictable, and in itself is an organizing factor in the student's educational life [13, p. 65].

With the help of a schedule, a sequence of preparation for the school day, for a lesson, if necessary, a visual diagram of the organization of the workspace, a set of necessary educational materials and sequentially compiled preparatory activities can be specially developed. This is extremely important, since it is difficult for such a child to perceive all the information by ear, and what is written often has the "degree of law." It is easier for him to look at the schedule himself and prepare the necessary items for the next lesson than to listen to the teacher's long instructions about what the next lesson will be and what should be left on the table.

The deeper the child's autistic maladjustment, the more attention should be paid to drawing up a schedule, since it serves as a means of orientation in the educational space and therefore, depending on how detailed the schedules are developed, how specific and visual they are in form, the more successful the socialization of children with ASD . In all cases, this should be addressed personally to the child, be present in his diary, a separate notebook or hang on the wall next to the child's desk, and consist of clear signs: drawings, photographs or inscriptions. It should also be borne in mind that such a child must be taught how to use a schedule.

As a result of this work, self-organization may significantly improve, and behavior problems associated with impulsivity, distraction, and difficulty switching may decrease. New activities presented as an addition, the development of a stable schedule, are more easily accepted by such a student, who usually rejects any attempts at change.

One of the important conditions for the effective inclusion of children with ASD in the general education environment is an adequate and positive attitude of the teacher towards children.

As Ph.D. writes. E.A. Gafari (2012) in his study, the positive attitude of teachers towards the inclusion of children with disabilities in general education is an effective way of social

integration for many categories of children with disabilities, since they not only receive a quality education, but are also successfully socialized, as well as integrate into the environment of their ordinary peers, get used to the fact that the same requirements are imposed on them as on all other students. This means that the school must create an organizational and pedagogical environment that allows the student to most flexibly build a student's educational route depending on his needs and choose the most optimal form of education. By organizational and pedagogical environment, we mean a set of specially organized pedagogical conditions for the development of the personality of a student with special educational needs [14].

One of the promising forms of adaptation for an autistic child is the subsequent gradual, individually dosed inclusion in a small subgroup of children with disabilities of communication and social development, where he has the opportunity to gain experience of being in a group, observing ordinary children with the supportive assistance of an adult.

Such assistance consists in constantly supporting students' self-confidence, providing them with a subjective experience of success with certain efforts. When working with students with ASD, it is necessary to create the calmest atmosphere possible in a lesson or lesson, maintain an atmosphere of goodwill, and also take an individual approach to each student, both in general education lessons and during special classes.

Thus, at present, the creation of an organizational and pedagogical environment is the main field of adaptation and training of a child with autism into an educational environment. Education is understood as "the promotion of the acquisition of skills or knowledge, including not only academic learning, but also socialization, language and communication, and the reduction of behavior problems to help the child develop independence and personal responsibility" [15, p. 28].

The general content of the curriculum for teaching children with ASD according to the Acting Order. The Minister of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated August 12, 2016 No. 499 is directed to:

1. Achieving goals and objectives presented in the form of expected learning outcomes;
2. Ensuring the principles of continuity and continuity, taking into account teaching, developmental and educational tasks between preschool education and training and primary education;
3. Creation of equal starting opportunities for training preschool children in the organization of primary education;
4. Formation of motor, communicative, cognitive, creative, social knowledge, skills, self-learning skills, including in young children;
5. Creation of psychological and pedagogical conditions for education and training;
6. Preparation for educational activities, taking into account the individual and age characteristics of students;
6. Formation of spiritual and moral skills based on national traditions and universal values within the framework of the implementation of the "Rukhanizhangyru" program;
7. Formation of social and personal qualities aimed at developing creativity, communication skills, critical thinking and teamwork skills;

Thus, the program for teaching children with ASD in the context of inclusive education presupposes an understanding of inclusion as a new philosophy of education, which is based on a modern humanistic approach to the education of children with disabilities, which consists in developing in those around them a positive social attitude towards the diversity of students and in

perceiving the individual characteristics of the child not as a problem, but as an opportunity to develop and enrich joint education for ordinary children and children with disabilities [16, p. 111].

Inclusive education of a student with autism requires the organization of mandatory regular and high-quality interaction between specialists in mass and special education, the opportunity to access information resources in the field of special psychology and correctional pedagogy, including electronic libraries, portals and websites, and remote advisory services. The organization of regular exchange of information between specialists of different profiles, specialists and families, including network resources and technologies, should be ensured.

In our opinion, the possibility of inclusive education is a big step towards solving a problem of the most important social significance, in which the interests of all participants in the educational process intersect.

REFERENCES

1. Semago N. Ya., Khotyleva T. Yu., Goncharenko M. S., Mikhalekova T. A. Education of children with autism spectrum disorders. Methodological recommendations for teachers and support specialists in primary schools // Ed. N. Ya. Semago. M.: 2012.
2. Volkmar, F. R. Autism: A Practical Guide for Parents, Family Members and Teachers. Ekaterinburg: 2014. 224 p.
3. Suleymenova R. A. Organizational and technological foundations of early correctional and pedagogical assistance to children with disabilities: Dis. slave.. Dr. ped. Sciences: Moscow, 2001. 460 p.
4. Barsanaeva D.S. Pedagogical conditions for the socialization of children at school through inclusive education. dis. slave...k. p.n. Bishkek: 2019.183 p.
5. Karabalaeva, G.T. The relationship between family and public education in modern conditions: Dis. working doctor ped. Sciences / Bishkek, 2016.
6. Nurmaganbetova R.K. Psychological and pedagogical problems of education in an inclusive environment in Kazakhstan. / Scientific aspect – 2019. No. 2. Access mode: // <https://na-journal.ru/2-2019-gumanitarnye-nauki/1606-psihologo-pedagogicheskie-problemy-obrazovaniya-v-inklyuzivnoi-srede-v-kazahstane>
7. Kaplieva A.K., Dautova K.A. Socialization of children with disabilities: problems and ways to solve them (2014) // access mode: <http://zkoipk.kz/ru/c1/438-conf.html>
8. Eralieva Kh.S. Introduction of inclusive education in Kazakhstan // Innovative pedagogical technologies: materials of the IV international. scientific conf. Kazan: Buk, 2016. pp. 26-28.
9. Jalmukhamedova A.K., Eshpanova D.D. Inclusive education in Kazakhstan: status, problems, prospects // Access mode: icie.ieml.ru
10. Movkebaeva Z.A., Denisova I.A., Oralkanova I.A., Zhakupova D.S. Inclusive education. Almaty, 2014. 200 p.
11. Sardarova Zh. I., Zhumasheva N. S. Inclusive and integrated education in the Republic of Kazakhstan // Scientific and methodological electronic journal "Concept". – 2017. – T. 35. – P. 113–116. Access mode: <http://e-koncept.ru/2017/771194.htm>
12. Development and implementation of models for including children with special needs in the general educational process. Guidelines. Astana: NAO named after I. Altynsarin, 2015. 48 p.

13. Psychological and pedagogical support for children with special educational needs in secondary schools: methodological recommendations / Eliseeva I.G., Ersarina A.K. - Almaty: NNPTsKP, 2019. 118 p.
14. Gafari E. A. Organizational and pedagogical conditions for teaching children with disabilities through inclusive education: on materials from the Islamic Republic of Iran: dissertation ... Ph.D. :Gafari E. A.; [Place of protection: Taj. state ped. University named after Sadriddin Aini] - Dushanbe, 2012. - 150 p.
15. Vigotskiy, L.S. Psychology / L.S. Vygotsky. – M.: EKSMO-Press, 2000. 1008 p.
16. Malofeev N.N. Inclusive education in the context of modern social policy // Defectology. – 2009. –No. 6.